

Resistance of IR varieties to leafhoppers and planthoppers

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We evaluated varieties IR5 to IR64 for resistance to rice green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*, in seedbox screening tests. Separate seedboxes were used for each insect species, with five replications per variety. Pregerminated rice seeds were sown in rows in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes. Ptb 33 and TN1 were the resistant and susceptible checks. At 7 d after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 20/variety and infested with 7-8 2d-instar nymphs of BPH or WBPH and 5 2d-instar GLH nymphs/ seedling. When the susceptible check died, damage was rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Resistance to GLH, BPH, and WBPH differed significantly (see table). IR62 and IR64 were highly resistant to all three insect species. IR28, IR52, IR54, IR56, IR58, IR62,

Resistance of IR varieties to GLH, BPH, and WBPH.

Variety	Damage rating ^a					
	GLH		BPH		WBPH	
IR5	6.6	e	5.4	d	5.4	d
IR8	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR20	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR22	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR24	5.4	d	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR26	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR28	1.0	a	5.4	d	5.4	d
IR29	6.2	e	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR30	5.4	d	9.0	f	6.2	cd
IR32	3.4	c	9.0	f	5.4	d
IR34	3.0	bc	9.0	f	5.4	c
IR36	2.6	b	6.6	e	5.0	c
IR38	5.4	d	9.0	f	6.6	e
IR40	6.6	e	6.6	e	6.6	e
IR42	2.6	b	5.2	de	5.0	c
IR46	6.6	e	4.6	c	5.4	d
IR48	2.6	b	3.4	b	3.0	b
IR50	3.4	c	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR52	1.0	a	2.6	b	1.4	a
IR54	1.0	a	6.6	e	2.6	b
IR56	1.4	a	3.4	b	2.6	b
IR58	1.0	a	5.4	d	3.4	b
IR60	3.4	c	5.4	d	5.4	d
IR62	1.0	a	1.4	a	1.4	a
IR64	1.0	a	1.0	a	1.0	a
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	1.0	a	1.0	a	1.0	a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f

^a Mean of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. Damage is rated on the 0-9 scale.

and IR64 were highly resistant to GLH; IR5, IR36, IR42, IR46, and

IR60 were moderately resistant to GLH, BPH, and WBPH. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

COLD TOLERANCE

Screening rice cultivars at seedling stage and anthesis for low-temperature tolerance in Madagascar

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Half the 1.2 million ha of rice in Madagascar is in the High Plateau, above 1,000 m altitude.

Two crops of rice can be grown a

year, although growing seasons differ by region. In Antananarivo (1,200 m), the first crop is sown Apr-May, transplanted Sep, and harvested Dec-Jan (see figure). Because low temperatures (min 9-11 °C) occur at the seedling stage, growth is very slow; farmers seldom transplant seedlings younger than 120 d. Second crop seeding is Oct-Nov, with harvest in Apr-May. Temperatures start decreasing in March but, depending on the altitude (800-1,300 m), may remain high enough (mean temp 22°C) for flowering and maturing.

In Antsirabe (1,500-2,000 m) only 1 crop is possible. Low temperature affects both seedling and ripening stages. Rice in Vinaninony-Fenomanana (1,900 m) has a more than 250-d duration.

To identify donor and outstanding cold-tolerant varieties, we studied the effects of low temperature at seedling and anthesis on 178 Malagasy accessions from the International Rice Germplasm Center (IRGC) and three from FOFIFA in the greenhouse and the IRRI phytotron.

Ten-day-old seedlings were